

MSProfileR report

I. Data loading

- Number of spectra loaded: 676

II. Preprocessing

Trimming

Parameters

- Minimum mass: 2000 m/z
- Maximum mass: 20000 m/z

Results

Conformity test

Results

Criteria	Results
Number of empty spectra	0
Number of irregular spectra	0
Number of different lengths	0

Parameters

- Exclude empty spectra: Yes
- Exclude irregular spectra: Yes

Cleaning

Parameters

- Method used to transform intensity: Sqrt
- Method used to smooth intensity: Savitsky-Golay
- Half window size: 10
- Method used to remove baseline: SNIP
- Number of iterations: 100
- Method used to calibrate intensity: TIC

Results

Culex_adamesi_PA_2 [A5]

Quality control

Parameters

- Scale estimator: Q
- Method used for the identification of atypical spectra: RC
- Threshold: 3
- Include lower spectra: Yes

Results

- Number of typical spectra: 667/676

- Number of atypical spectra: 9/676
- Atypical spectra: 137: *Culex dunni*_PA_29 [A5], 138: *Culex dunni*_PA_29 [A6], 165: *Culex idottus*_PA_5 [B5], 166: *Culex idottus*_PA_5 [B6], 167: *Culex idottus*_PA_5 [B7], 168: *Culex idottus*_PA_5 [B8], 372: *Culex portesi*_PA_34 [C4], 626: *Culex usquatus*_PA_83 [E11], 628: *Culex usquatus*_PA_83 [E9]

Averaging

Parameters

- Method: Mean

Results

- Number of spectra before merging: 667
- Number of spectra after merging: 168

III. Processing

Peak detection

Parameters

- Noise estimator method: MAD
- Half window size:
- SNR: 3

Results

Average number of peaks for SNR 3: 113.24 (sd: 24.02)

Culex_adamesi_PA_2 [A5 A6 A7 A8]

Spectrum alignment

Parameters

- Method for reference peaks: MAD
- Minimum frequency of reference peaks: 0.5
- Tolerance for reference peaks: 0.002
- Warping method for alignment: Lowess

Results

- Number of reference peaks: 46

193329.7 m/z
18248.7 m/z
17167.7 m/z
16086.7 m/z
15005.7 m/z
13924.7 m/z
12843.7 m/z
11762.7 m/z
10681.7 m/z
9600.7 m/z
8519.6 m/z
7438.6 m/z
6357.6 m/z
5276.6 m/z
4195.6 m/z
3114.6 m/z
20333.6 m/z

Peak binning

Parameters

- Method for binning: Strict
- Tolerance for reference binning: 0.002

Results

Number of peaks: 786

Peak filtering

Parameters

- Minimum frequency: 0.2

Results

Number of peaks: 213

Intensity matrix

Parameters

- Fill missing intensities using the aligned spectra: Yes

Results

IV. Annotations

Names	Values
Number of annotations	169
Number of spectra	169
Number of annotation without spectrum	0
Number of spectra without annotation	0